

GRAPHENE-REINFORCED CHITOSAN/PDMS MORPHING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Synthetic morphing composites can change their shape actively in response to triggers and have great potential for applications as sensors, soft actuators, in robotics and biomedicine. In this study, graphene-reinforced chitosan/polydimethylsiloxane bi-layered morphing composites are developed, leveraging their differential coefficient of thermal expansion to enable different volume changes within each layer. UV photo-polymerisation/crosslinking serves to improve the bi-layer interface and prevent delamination during morphing. It is possible to design accurate patterned bi-layered structures with the aid of mask-less dynamic light photolithography (DLP). Upon activation by thermal triggers, the bi-layered composite achieves rapid, reversible and multi-repeatable morphing. A finite element model is developed to simulate the deflection of the sample due to anisotropic thermal expansion of the bi-layer. The model can predict the deflection of the bi-layered composite with a relative error of 3.3 % in comparison to experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Morphing materials can exhibit active shape change in response to external stimuli. The biological world provides inspiration for the design and application of synthetic morphing materials. Inspired by the structure of pine cone scales, here a bi-layer-structure is investigated as a synthetic morphing composite. Owing to the different properties of layers, such as their coefficients of thermal expansion or coefficients of hygroscopic expansion, the upper and lower layers can experience different changes in volume. As a result, the composites can achieve various morphing behaviours such as bending or twisting depending on their configuration. In this work, chitosan has been chosen as a material for one of the layers due to its very low coefficient of thermal expansion. Whereas the other layer is formed of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), which has a coefficient of thermal expansion more than five times that of chitosan. Based on the mechanism of differential thermal expansion, thermal-related triggers, both direct heating and indirect photo-thermal heating can actuate morphing.

For bi-layered composites, delamination due to weak interfaces is a significant issue affecting morphing performance. Physical surface modification, such as low-temperature, low-pressure air plasma treatment, enables improvement of the surface wetting properties of otherwise hydrophobic PDMS. However, post-plasma treatment PDMS undergoes relatively fast hydrophobic recovery under

ambient conditions. Consequently, further chemical surface modification for PDMS is necessary to obtain bi-layered composites with strong interfacial bonding.

Since single layer graphene was firstly mechanically exfoliated at the University of Manchester in 2004 [1], graphene has received significant attention worldwide. Graphene has ultra-high thermal, electrical conductivity and mechanical properties. In addition, graphene has been reported to have a negative coefficient of thermal expansion [2]. Importantly, graphene is able to absorb (near) infrared light and convert light energy to heat [3]. Pure graphene is also incredibly flexible as it has a thickness of only one-atom. With the addition of graphene or indeed reduced graphene oxide (rGO), it is possible to improve both thermal and mechanical properties of the composite effectively. In this work rGO is selected to enable photo-thermal triggering.

2 EXPERIMENTS AND SIMULATION

2.1 Materials

Chitosan (medium molecular weight), methacrylic anhydride, (3-mercaptopropyl) trimethoxysilane (MTS), 2-hydroxy-4'-(2-hydroxyethoxy)-2-methylpropiophenone (Irgacure 2959), L-ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and all chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (UK). Graphite (grade: 2369) was supplied by Graphexel Ltd (UK), and PDMS (Sylgard184) was purchased from Dow Corning (UK).

2.2 Preparation of Graphene-reinforced Chitosan Solution

Chitosan solutions (2 wt% in acetic acid) were prepared by dissolving chitosan powder in 0.61 mol% (equivalent to 2 wt%) acetic acid solution and magnetically stirred overnight. Chitosan was functionalised for eventual photo-polymerisation using 0.4 molar equivalents of methacrylic anhydride, added dropwise into the 2 wt% chitosan solution at room temperature (RT) for 3 h under constant stirring, following [4]. The solution was then dialysed against deionised water for one week with regular water changes and subsequently lyophilized at -50 °C.

Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared by the modified Hummer's method [5]. 0.2 mg/ml GO aqueous solution was reduced by 0.02 wt% vitamin C under ammonia controlled alkali condition (pH: 9-10) and 95°C for 15 min [6].

Freeze-dried methacrylamide chitosan was then weighed, dissolved into deionised water and magnetic stirred overnight to give 2 wt% aqueous solution. The rGO aqueous solution was added into methacrylamide chitosan solution dropwise under constant stirring. The photoinitiator, Irgacure 2959, was added into the methacrylamide chitosan-rGO solution at 1 wt%.

2.3 Preparation and Functionalisation of PDMS

PDMS films were spin coated, then plasma treated and subsequently thiolated for eventual thiol-ene click photo-polymerisation with methacrylamide chitosan. PDMS and its crosslinker were mixed by the weight ratio of 10:1, respectively, according to the manufacturer's instructions. The mixture was degassed for 30 min in a dessicator and then spin coated in a polystyrene Petri dish (10 cm diameter) using a speed of 800 rpm for 1 min. The resulting thin film was cured overnight at 70 °C in an oven. The cured PDMS film was then plasma treated using a bespoke lab made low-temperature, low-pressure plasma treatment rig for 5 min (air plasma) to increase the number of polar groups on the surface. Immediately post-plasma treatment the film was thiolated following a modified process [7], briefly, the film was immersed in 10 wt% MTS ethyl acetate solution and left under continuous shaking for 3 h at 37 °C (Lab Companion SI-600 shaker). The thiolated PDMS film was then rinsed in methanol twice and dichloromethane in between at RT and dried under nitrogen prior to photo-polymerisation with the methacrylamide chitosan-rGO, which formed the other layer, detailed below.

2.4 UV Photo-polymerisation

A layer of methacrylamide chitosan-rGO aqueous solution was screened on the thiolated PDMS film surface using a glass microscope slide, and then exposed to UV irradiation (at 365 nm, 6.5 mW/cm²) under air atmosphere for 5 min. The cured composite was rinsed by deionised water three times to remove any unreacted residues and finally dried overnight in an oven at 25 °C.

2.5 Characterisation

Water-in-air contact angles on control and plasma treated PDMS were determined using a Kruss DSA-100 Drop Shape Analyzer (Germany). Contact angle measurements were taken over a period of 48 h to determine hydrophobic recovery ($n=5$). Bi-layered films were sectioned using a fine double edged razor blade and their morphology and layer thicknesses determined by scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM and EDS, Quanta 250 FEG, FEI, USA) and subsequent image analysis (Image J). The morphology of rGO flakes was characterised by transmission electron microscope (TEM, Philips CM 20, USA). During morphing tests the sample temperature was recorded using an infrared camera (FLIR AX5, UK). The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of PDMS and methacrylamide chitosan-rGO were measured using a dilatometer (NETZSCH DIL402PC, Germany) using a temperature range 30 °C to 200 °C with the heating rate of 2 °C/min. The elastic Young's modulus of the methacrylamide chitosan-rGO films was tested using a nanoindenter (MTS System Corporation, Nano Indenter[®] XP, USA). Two different positions on each chitosan-rGO film sample were tested and 25 nanoindentations were made at each position.

2.6 Morphing Composite Modelling using Finite Element Analysis

Finite element analysis (FEA) determines the values at different points, in a domain, of physical variables such as displacement, stress, strain and temperature [8]. The FEA model, to simulate the bending of the morphing composites, was created in the commercially available package Abaqus. Each layer of the morphing composite was modelled as a 2D geometry, representing the length and thickness of the physical sample. Rigid body motion of the model was constrained by applying a kinematic boundary condition that fixed the displacements and rotations of the constrained end (Figure 1). The interface was modelled by tying the degrees of freedom at the bottom and the top edge of methacrylamide chitosan-rGO and PDMS, respectively. Temperature increase was applied uniformly to the virtual sample.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the geometric model.

Each of the layers was assumed isotropic, linear elastic, and homogenous. The mechanical and thermal properties were considered constant in the simulation temperature range (26 °C to 50 °C). Some mechanical and thermal properties of chitosan and PDMS used in the model were obtained from literature [9]–[12]. However, the values used for coefficient of thermal expansion and Young's modulus of methacrylamide chitosan-rGO were based on measurements obtained by dilatometry and nanoindentation, as these values are either not available or inconsistent in the literature. The material properties used in the model as given below in Table 1.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio (m/m)	Specific Heat (J/kg K)	CTE (ppm/K)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m K)	Thickness (μ m)	Length (mm)
PDMS	1030	1.8 [#]	0.49	1591 ^{##}	322	0.15 [*]	72	8
Chitosan- rGO	796 ^{**}	7400	0.45	1610 ^{**}	45	0.21 ^{**}	10	8

Table 1: Material properties used in the FEA model. (Information adopted from references: [#][9], ^{##}[10], ^{*}[11], and ^{**}[12])

The geometric model was discretised with 8-node biquadratic displacement, bilinear temperature, reduced integration finite elements, identified in Abaqus with code: CPS8RT. Each layer consisted of four elements through thickness for any element size. A mesh sensitivity study was carried out to optimize the computational time. The maximum deflection of the virtual sample converges at a minimum number of 640 elements as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Plot of the mesh sensitivity analysis for the deflection.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 rGO Characterisation

It has been reported that vitamin C can reduce graphene oxide and provide stable reduced graphene oxide (rGO) aqueous solution without aggregation [6]. Vitamin C was used here to reduce the graphene oxide aqueous solution in order to obtain a good dispersion of graphene in methacrylamide chitosan aqueous solution. The average rGO flake widths are several micrometres without aggregation, shown in the SEM below (Figure 3(a)). TEM image of rGO flakes in Figure 3 (b) demonstrates that the rGO flakes have a few layers with wrinkles and crumples on the surface.

Figure 3: (a) SEM image and (b) TEM image of rGO flakes.

3.2 Surface Modification and Hydrophobic Recovery

The surface of unmodified PDMS is relatively hydrophobic and requires surface treatment to produce bi-layered materials with suitable interfaces. Plasma treatment is a powerful physical method to enhance the surface wetting ability of materials. After five-minute plasma treatment, the water contact angle of the surface decreases from 96.8° to 16.1° . Hydrophobic recovery of treated PDMS occurs relatively quickly under ambient conditions. After one hour of plasma treatment the water contact angle recovers by 69.5 % of the untreated PDMS and 87.1 % after 48 h (shown in Figure 4, below). These results are in line with a study on oxygen plasma treatment on PDMS [13].

Figure 4: Water contact angle change of plasma-treated PDMS surface as a function of recovery time.

The fast hydrophobic recovery of PDMS surface affects further manufacture and morphing performance of the bi-layered composite. Thiolation of the PDMS enables enhanced interface with its counterpart methacrylamide chitosan layer by thiol-ene click photo-polymerisation [14] and covalent bond formation at the interface. This interface provides a reliable bonding for the bi-layered composite

and avoids potential delamination problems encountered when PDMS or plasma-treated PDMS formed a bi-layer with chitosan or methacrylamide chitosan. The thickness of the layers was confirmed using SEM-EDS in Figure 5. The SEM-EDS maps demonstrate that the methacrylamide chitosan-rGO layer with strong C and N signals has the thickness of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ and the PDMS layer, rich in Si and O elements, has the thickness of $\sim 70 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5: SEM and EDS maps for cross-section of graphene-reinforced chitosan/PDMS composite.

3.3 Morphing Evaluation and FEA Model

Morphing behaviour was recorded using the infrared camera as the bi-layered composite is thermally activated from 26°C to 50°C , example stills at selected time points are given in Figure 6. According to the image analysis, the morphing deflection is 1.32 mm (Figure 6 (c)). Morphing behaviour was reversible and repeatable. After three repetitions, the recovery ratio stabilised at 80 % of the first morphing. We hypothesise that this is due to moisture in the methacrylamide chitosan layer evaporating.

Figure 6: Bi-layered composite shown in the dash square, which is held in a vertical configuration, with the bottom end free. (a) Initial position at 26°C before morphing. (b) Final position at 50°C during the morphing. (c) Morphing deflection measurement (1.32 mm).

The FEA model predicts a deflection of 1.27 mm and bending towards the methacrylamide chitosan-rGO layer (top surface in the model below). The displacement contour plot and deformed shape are shown in Figure 7. The relative error between experimental and simulation results can be attributed to the uneven heating in the experiment, the pre-strain and edge defects on the sample in addition to non-homogenous properties and thickness of the material system.

Figure 7: Displacement contour plot of the FEA model. Units: m.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Thiol-ene click photo-polymerisation solves the issue of weak interface encountered in bi-layered composite structures effectively. The graphene-reinforced chitosan/PDMS bi-layered composites developed in this study morph rapidly, reversibly and repeatedly under the induction of thermal triggers. The FEA model estimates the deflection simulation of the bi-layered composite with a relative error of 3.3 % in comparison to experiment results, giving confidence to the assumed material properties and representation of the interface. The error of the model might be reduced if the pre-strain of the physical sample and non-uniform heating are considered in the analysis. The FEA simulation confirms that the morphing behaviour of the graphene-reinforced chitosan/PDMS composite is driven by differential thermal expansion.

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